

Discovery of potential Zika virus NS3^{pro} inhibitors from the small molecule BraCoLi library

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Figure S1. Docking poses of **BR010385** and **BR010384** to the ZIKV NS3^{pro}. **(A) BR010385** (cyan) predicted interactions with residues such as Asp129, Gly153, Val155, and Tyr161, as well as Ser81 and Asp83 (NS2B, orange). A similar pose was observed for was observed for **(B) BR010384** (salmon), despite having predicted interactions only with Asp129 and Tyr161. The ZIKV NS3^{pro} (slate) is shown as a transparent cartoon. Residues are shown as sticks and labeled. Predicted interactions are shown as dashed yellow lines. Images were generated with PyMOL (v.2.5.7).

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Figure S2. Half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) curve of compound **BR020255** against ZIKV NS2B-NS3^{pro}. Assays were performed in 10 mM Tris-HCl, 5% v/v glycerin, and 0.005% Tween 20 at pH 8.5, in the presence of 2 nM enzyme and 44 μM substrate, at 37 °C. IC₅₀ values are represented as the average and standard deviation calculated from two independent assays in triplicate ($n = 6$ data points).

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